

IQTISODIYOT&TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

№5 (3)

ISSN: 2992-8982 <https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz/>

2026

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Bosh muharrir:

Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich

*Elektron nashr. 2026-yil, may.
3-qism*

Bosh muharrir o'rinbosari:

Karimov Norboy G'aniyevich

Muharrir:

Qurbonov Sherzod Ismatillayevich

Tahrir hay'ati:

Salimov Oqil Umrzoqovich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Abduraxmanov Kalandar Xodjayevich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Rae Kvon Chung, Janubiy Koreya, TDIU faxriy professori, "Nobel" mukofoti laureati
Osman Mesten, Turkiya parlamenti a'zosi, Turkiya – O'zbekiston do'stlik jamiyati rahbari
Axmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Kalonov Muxiddin Baxritdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Siddiqova Sadoqat G'afforovna, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Xudoyqulov Sadirdin Karimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Maxmudov Nosir, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Samadov Asqarjon Nishonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, professor
Slizovskiy Dimitriy Yegorovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Ikrom Akramovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abdug'aniyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xajiyev Baxtiyor Dushaboyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Hakimov Nazar Hakimovich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Musayeva Shoirazimovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), professor
Ali Konak (Ali Ko'nak), iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor (Turkiya)
Cham Tat Huei, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD), professor (Malayziya)
Foziljonov Ibrohimjon Sotvoldixo'ja o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dots.
Faxridinov Zafarjon Faxridin o'g'li, O'zb. Res. Bosh prokuraturasi HIJQKD boshqarma boshlig'i
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, Anijon viloyati prokurorining o'rinbosari
Ochilov Farkhod, O'zb. Res. Bosh prokuraturasi IJQK Departamentining Namangan viloyati boshqarmasi boshlig'i
Buzrukxonov Sarvarxon Munavvarxonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Axmedov Javohir Jamolovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Toxirov Jaloliddin Ochil o'g'li, texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), katta o'qituvchi
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), v.b. dots.
Djudi Smetana, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Krissi Lyuis, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Glazova Marina Viktorovna, Iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (Moskva)
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD) (Turkiya)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhamatjon o'g'li, TDIU ITI departamenti rahbari
Ochilov Bobur Baxtiyor o'g'li, TDIU katta o'qituvchisi
Golisheva Yelena Vyacheslavovna, Iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent.
Abdulkarimova Dinara Rustamxonovna, bank-moliya akademiyasi professori, DSc., professor.
Ikramov Murod Akramovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Nazarova Ra'no Rustamovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Editorial board:

Salimov Okil Umrzokovich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan
Abdurakhmanov Kalandar Khodjayevich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Rae Kwon Chung, South Korea, Honorary Professor at TSUE, Nobel Prize Laureate
Osman Mesten, Member of the Turkish Parliament, Head of the Turkey–Uzbekistan Friendship Society
Akhmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Akhmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Abdurakhmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Kalonov Mukhiddin Bakhridinovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Siddikova Sadokat Gafforovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogical Sciences
Khudoykulov Sadirdin Karimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Makhmudov Nosir, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Samadov Askarjon Nishonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Professor
Slizovskiy Dmitriy Yegorovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Akhmedov Ikrom Akramovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abduganiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khajiyev Bakhtiyor Dushaboyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khakimov Nazar Khakimovich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Professor
Ali Konak, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor (Turkey)
Cham Tat Huei, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD), Professor (Malaysia)
Foziljonov Ibrokhimjon Sotvoldikhoja ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Fakhriddinov Zafarjon Fakhriddin ogli, Head of the DCEC under the Prosecutor General's Office of the Rep. of Uzb.
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, Deputy Prosecutor of Anijan Region
Ochilov Farkhod, Head of the Namangan Regional Department of the Department of Internal Affairs of Rep. of Uzb.
Buzrukkhonov Sarvarkhon Munavvarkhonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Akhmedov Javokhir Jamolovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences
Tokhirov Jaloliddin Ochil ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Technical Sciences, Senior Lecturer
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Acting Associate Professor
Judi Smetana, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)
Chrissy Lewis, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)
Glazova Marina Victorovna, Doctor of Sciences in Economics (Moscow)
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin kizi, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) (Turkey)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhamatjon ugli, Head of the Department of Scientific Research and Innovations, TSUE
Ochilov Bobur Bakhtiyor ugli, Senior lecturer at TSUI
Golisheva Yelena Vyacheslavovna, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Abdukarimova Dinara Rustamkhanovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Ikramov Murod Akramovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Nazarova Ra'no Rustamovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Ekspertlar kengashi:

Berkinov Bazarbay, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Po'latov Baxtiyor Alimovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Aliyev Bekdavlat Aliyevich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Rustamov Ilhomiddin, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Hakimov Ziyodulla Ahmadovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
G'afurov Doniyor Orifovich, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Tuxtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Xamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarim qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Yaxshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, katta o'qituvchi
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, mustaqil tadqiqotchi
Komilova Nilufar Karshiboyevna, Geografiya fanlari doktori, professori
Umirzoqov Ja'sur Artiqboy o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent
Zebo Kuldasheva, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent

Board of Experts:

Berkinov Bazarbay, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Pulatov Bakhtiyor Alimovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Aliyev Bekdavlat Aliyevich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Rustamov Ilhomiddin, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Khakimov Ziyodulla Akhmadovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics
Gafurov Doniyor Orifovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogy
Fayziyev Oybek Rakhimovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Tukhtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Khamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarimovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Yakhshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, Senior Lecturer
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, Independent Researcher
Komilova Nilufar Karshiboyevna, Doctor of Geographical Sciences, Professor
Umirzokov Jasur Artiqboy ugli, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Associate Professor
Zebo Kuldasheva, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Associate Professor

- 08.00.01 Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.05 Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.06 Ekonometrika va statistika
- 08.00.07 Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
- 08.00.08 Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 Marketing
- 08.00.12 Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 Menejment
- 08.00.14 Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

Muassis: "Ma'rifat-print-media" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti, O'zR Tabiat resurslari vazirligi, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi huzuridagi IJQK departamenti.

Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

“Yashil” iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot” jurnali

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasi rayosatining 2023-yil 1-apreldagi 336/3-sonli qarori bilan ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

MUNDARIJA

O'ZBEKISTONDA NAQDSIZ TO'LOVLAR ULUSHINING OSHISHI VA PUL MASSASI NAZORATI SAMARADORLIGIGA TA'SIRI	28
Pardayev G'ayrat Jabbor o'g'li	
BUXGALTERIYA HISOBINING PAYDO BO'LISHI VA RIVOJLANISHI HISOB SIYOSATINING SHAKLLANISHIDA ASOS SIFATIDA	34
Abdovaxidov Farxod Tuychiyevich	
O'ZBEKISTON AUDITORLIK TASHKILOTLARIDA ICHKI SIFAT NAZORATI STANDARTLARINI RISKKA YO'NALTIRILGAN YONDASHUV ASOSIDA TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	41
Bobonarova Kamola	
SANOAT KORXONALARINING INVESTITSION-INNOVATSION FAOLIYATI SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHNING NAZARIY-USLUBIY ASOSLARI	47
Azizova Habiba Arslonovna	
TADBIRKORLIK SUBYEKTLARIGA RAQAMLI DAVLAT XIZMATLARINI KO'RSATISHNING NAZARIY YONDASHUHLARI	56
Yusupova Dilbar Mirabidovna	
КАРБОНОВЫЕ КРЕДИТЫ В АГРАРНОМ СЕКТОРЕ КАК ИНСТРУМЕНТ РАЗВИТИЯ ЗЕЛЁНОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАНА	61
Абдуллаева Зайнаб Руслановна	
BUXORO ZINDONI VA BOLO HOVUZ ANSAMBLI MISOLIDA TARIXIY OBIDALARNING BARQAROR TURISTIK SIG'IMI TAHLILI	66
Shodiyeva Moxichehra Shokir qizi, Qilichov Muhridin Husniddin o'g'li	
SOLIQ TIZIMIDA SOLIQ RISKINI BAHOLASH USLUBIYOTI	73
Ravshanjon Azimovich	
O'ZBEKISTONDA UMUMIY O'RTA TA'LIM TIZIMI: RIVOJLANISH TENDENSIYALARI VA BUXORO VILOYATI TAHLILI.....	80
Davidxodjayev Oybek Obidovich	
O'ZBEKISTONDA INVESTITSION KREDITLASHLASHNING AMALDAGI HOLATI VA ISTIQBOLLARI.....	85
Abdurashidova Mohidil Qodir qizi, Karimova A.	
IQTISODIYOTNI TRANSFORMATSIYALASH SHAROITIDA DXSH ASOSIDA FAOLIYAT YURITAYOTGAN TADBIRKORLIK SUBYEKTLARINI MOLIVAVIY QO'LLAB-QUVVATLASHNI BAHOLASH USULLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH MUAMMOLARI	91
Toxirov Jaxongir Maxmudjon o'g'li	
SURXONDARYO VILOYATIDA UY-JOY QURILISHI VA IPOTEKA KREDITLASHNING O'ZARO BOG'LIQLIGI	96
Turopova Nigora Xolmurod qizi, Safarova Dilrabo Baxriddin qizi	
ESG INTEGRATION AND GREEN FINANCIAL ANALYSIS: A NEW METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH TO CORPORATE FINANCIAL SUSTAINABILITY	100
Erkin Temirovich Shodiev	
THE CURRENT STATE OF DIGITALIZATION OF TOURISM IN UZBEKISTAN AND PROSPECTS FOR ITS DEVELOPMENT	105
Bekmurodov Bakhtiyor Farkhodovich	
TA'LIM MUASSASALARINI MOLIVALASHTIRISHDA OPTIMALLASHTIRISH ZARURATI VA YO'NALISHLARI.....	113
Umarov Avzaljon Yodgorali o'g'li	
AHOLI ISTE'MOL MADANIYATI VA MILLIY IQTISODIY O'SISHGA TA'SIRI	118
Rustamov Sherov Oblokulovich	

ISHLAB CHIQRARISH OMILLARINING IQTISODIY O'SISHGA TA'SIRI: KOBБ-DOUGLAS MODELII ASOSIDA EKONOMETRIK TAHLIL	123
Maxmudov Sobir Xudoyberdiyevich	
BARQAROR SHAHARSOZLIK RIVOJLANISHIGA ERISHISHDA QATTIQ CHIQUINDILARNI KOMPLEKS BOSHQARISH	129
Firas Halawani, Feruza Insavaliyeva	
СРАВНИТЕЛЬНЫЙ АНАЛИЗ РЕАЛИЗАЦИИ НА НАЦИОНАЛЬНОМ УРОВНЕ КЛЮЧЕВЫХ МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫХ ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ СОГЛАШЕНИЙ, СВЯЗАННЫХ С ТРАНСГРАНИЧНЫМ ЗАГРЯЗНЕНИЕМ, В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ И СОСЕДНИХ СТРАНАХ.....	139
Шафикова Луиза, Ойбек Камилов	
ЦИФРОВАЯ ЭКОНОМИКА УЗБЕКИСТАНА: ОЦЕНКА ТЕКУЩЕГО УРОВНЯ И ПОТЕНЦИАЛА РОСТА	150
Омонтурдиева Диёра	
YER VA SUV RESURLARINI INTEGRATSIYALASHGAN BOSHQARISHDA DRONLARDAN FOYDALANISH.....	155
Matkarimov Mansur	
YASHIL INVESTITSIYALAR BOZORI MEKANIZMINING DASTAKLARI	161
Ziyodullayeva Gulasal Akmal qizi	
СТРАТЕГИЯ ПРИВЛЕЧЕНИЯ И УДЕРЖАНИЯ ПЕРСОНАЛА ПОСРЕДСТВОМ HR-БРЕНДИНГА: ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЕ ОСНОВЫ И ПРАКТИКА РЕАЛИЗАЦИИ В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ УЗБЕКИСТАН	167
Дониерова Фотимабону Алишер кизи	
KAMBAG'ALLIKNI MONETAR VA KO'P O'LCHOVLI VAHOLASH METODOLOGIYASI ASOSIDA IQTISODIY O'SISH STRATEGIYALARINI KONSEPTUAL TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	173
Sotiboldiyev Asadbek Hasan o'g'li	
QURILISH SANOATIDA RESURS TEJAMKOR ISHLAB CHIQRARISH TIZIMINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING USTUVOR YO'NALISHLARI.....	179
Utbasarov Doniyorjon Baxtiyorovich	
KICHIK BIZNESDA XIZMATLAR SOHASINI RAQAMLI TEKNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA RIVOJLANTIRISHNING AHAMIYATI.....	188
Raximov Zafar Komilovich, Mamatazimov Jaloliddin Sherzod o'g'li	
MANAGING DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION IN PRIMARY HEALTHCARE: A SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW	192
Ashurova Sitara Xusnitdin qizi	

MANAGING DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION IN PRIMARY HEALTHCARE: A SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW

Ashurova Sitora Xusnitdin qizi

PhD candidate

Westminster International University in Tashkent

Orcid: 0009-0002-0637-3281

E-mail: sit.ashurova@wiut.uz

Abstract. Digital transformation is increasingly recognized as a key factor in improving efficiency and service quality in primary healthcare. This study conducts a systematic literature review using the PRISMA approach to examine the factors influencing digital transformation and its impact on organizational performance. Relevant peer-reviewed studies published between 2015 and 2025 were identified through a structured database search. The findings indicate that digital transformation is shaped by technological, organizational, and environmental factors. In addition, transformation processes play a mediating role in improving organizational performance. The review also highlights a significant research gap in developing countries, including Uzbekistan, and provides a foundation for future empirical studies.

Key words: Digital transformation, Primary healthcare, Organizational performance, Systematic literature review, Emerging economies, Healthcare management.

Annotatsiya. Raqamli transformatsiya sog'liqni saqlashning birlamchi bo'g'inida xizmat ko'rsatish samaradorligi va sifatini oshirishning asosiy omili sifatida tobora muhim ahamiyat kasb etmoqda. Ushbu tadqiqotda raqamli transformatsiyaga ta'sir etuvchi omillar va uning tashkilot samaradorligiga ta'sirini o'rganish maqsadida PRISMA yondashuvi asosida tizimli adabiyotlar sharhi amalga oshirildi. 2015–2025-yillar oralig'ida nashr etilgan tegishli, ekspertlar tomonidan taqrizdan o'tkazilgan ilmiy maqolalar tizimli ma'lumotlar bazasi qidiruvi orqali tanlab olindi. Natijalar shuni ko'rsatdiki, raqamli transformatsiya texnologik, tashkiliy va institutsional omillar ta'sirida shakllanadi. Bundan tashqari, transformatsiya jarayonlari tashkilot samaradorligini oshirishda vositachilik rolini bajaradi. Tadqiqot, shuningdek, rivojlanayotgan mamlakatlarda, jumladan O'zbekistonda, ushbu yo'nalishdagi ilmiy tadqiqotlar yetarli emasligini ko'rsatadi hamda kelgusidagi empirik tadqiqotlar uchun nazariy asos yaratadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Raqamli transformatsiya, Birlamchi tibbiy yordam, Tashkilot samaradorligi, Tizimli adabiyotlar sharhi, Rivojlanayotgan mamlakatlar, Sog'liqni saqlash boshqaruvi.

Аннотация. Цифровая трансформация все чаще рассматривается как ключевой фактор повышения эффективности и качества услуг в системе первичной медико-санитарной помощи. В данном исследовании проводится систематический обзор литературы с использованием подхода PRISMA с целью выявления факторов, влияющих на цифровую трансформацию, а также её воздействия на организационную эффективность. В выборку вошли рецензируемые научные статьи, опубликованные в период 2015–2025 годов и отобранные на основе структурированного поиска по базам данных. Результаты показывают, что цифровая трансформация формируется под воздействием технологических, организационных и институциональных факторов. Кроме того, процессы трансформации выполняют посредническую роль в повышении организационной эффективности. Обзор также выявляет существенный исследовательский пробел в отношении развивающихся стран, включая Узбекистан, и формирует основу для дальнейших эмпирических исследований.

Ключевые слова: Цифровая трансформация, Первичная медико-санитарная помощь, Организационная эффективность, Систематический обзор литературы, Развивающиеся страны, Управление здравоохранением.

INTRODUCTION

Over the past decade, digital transformation has become a strategic priority in healthcare systems worldwide, aiming to improve efficiency, service quality, and access to healthcare services [1]. Technologies such as electronic medical records, telemedicine, and integrated health information systems are increasingly

being implemented to support these objectives [2]. In Uzbekistan, the digitalization of the healthcare sector has accelerated through national initiatives, including the “Digital Uzbekistan – 2030” Strategy, which emphasizes the modernization of primary healthcare services [3].

Technology adoption has traditionally been explained using the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), which identifies perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use as the key determinants of user behavior [8]. However, such models generally assume relatively stable organizational environments and voluntary technology use, which do not fully reflect the complexity of healthcare settings. In practice, digital system use is often mandatory, while user behavior evolves through continuous interaction with technology, institutional conditions, and organizational culture [9]. Consequently, initial positive perceptions do not always result in sustained and effective system utilization.

To better capture these dynamics, this study adopts Adaptive Structuration Theory as its theoretical foundation. This perspective explains how technology use evolves through the interaction between users, organizational structures, and institutional practices [10]. Accordingly, the present study examines how healthcare providers adapt to digital medical systems within primary healthcare settings.

The existing literature reveals several important research gaps, including limited attention to primary healthcare organizations, insufficient empirical evidence from developing countries such as Uzbekistan, and the absence of integrated frameworks addressing post-adoption dynamics and organizational adaptation processes [11]. Therefore, this study aims to contribute to the literature by systematically reviewing existing research on digital transformation management in primary healthcare and identifying the main technological, organizational, and environmental factors affecting implementation outcomes.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Digital transformation in healthcare has been widely associated with improvements in operational efficiency, service delivery, and patient outcomes [12]. The integration of digital technologies such as electronic medical records, telemedicine platforms, and integrated health information systems enables better coordination of care, enhances communication among healthcare providers, and supports evidence-based decision-making processes [13]. These benefits are particularly important in primary healthcare settings, where timely access to accurate patient information directly influences the quality, continuity, and effectiveness of healthcare services.

At the same time, existing studies indicate that digital transformation does not automatically lead to improved organizational performance [14]. The effectiveness of digital systems depends on several interrelated factors, including system reliability, infrastructure readiness, interoperability, staff competencies, and compatibility with clinical workflows [15]. In some healthcare organizations, insufficiently integrated or poorly implemented systems have increased administrative burden, disrupted workflows, and reduced efficiency instead of improving service quality [16].

Furthermore, the literature emphasizes that healthcare digitalization is not solely a technological process but also an organizational and managerial transformation [17]. Successful implementation requires organizational readiness, leadership support, employee engagement, and continuous adaptation of work processes [18]. In developing countries, additional challenges such as limited financial resources, insufficient technical infrastructure, and institutional constraints may further affect the sustainability of digital transformation initiatives [19].

These findings suggest that digital transformation in primary healthcare should be understood as a complex socio-technical process shaped by technological, organizational, and environmental factors that continuously interact with one another [17].

To better address these complexities, Adaptive Structuration Theory provides a dynamic theoretical framework for understanding technology use in organizational settings. Unlike traditional technology adoption models, this theory emphasizes that users do not passively accept technological systems; rather, they actively interpret, adapt, and reshape technology through their interaction with organizational structures and everyday practices [10].

In healthcare environments, this adaptive process becomes especially visible when healthcare professionals develop alternative workflows or temporary solutions to cope with system limitations and operational challenges [20]. Such adaptive behaviors demonstrate that technology use evolves over time and is strongly influenced by organizational culture, institutional conditions, managerial practices, and user experience.

From this perspective, digital transformation should not be viewed as a one-time implementation initiative but rather as a continuous and evolving organizational process [21]. The effectiveness of digital systems depends not only on the availability of technology but also on how healthcare organizations manage adaptation, learning, communication, and process integration over time.

Accordingly, this theoretical perspective provides a valuable foundation for understanding how technological, organizational, and environmental factors interact to shape digital transformation outcomes in primary healthcare settings. It also supports the development of more comprehensive frameworks for analyzing post-adoption dynamics and organizational performance in healthcare institutions, particularly within developing country contexts such as Uzbekistan.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study employs a systematic literature review approach based on the PRISMA framework in order to ensure a transparent, structured, and replicable study selection process. The PRISMA approach was selected because it provides clear procedures for identifying, screening, evaluating, and synthesizing relevant academic literature in a systematic manner.

Relevant studies were identified through structured searches conducted in major international academic databases, including Scopus, Web of Science, and PubMed. These databases were selected due to their extensive coverage of peer-reviewed publications in healthcare management, information systems, and digital transformation research.

The search process utilized combinations of keywords and Boolean operators, including “digital transformation,” “primary healthcare,” “healthcare management,” “electronic health systems,” “organizational performance,” and “health information systems.” Additional filtering criteria were applied to improve the relevance and quality of the selected studies.

The inclusion criteria required studies to:

- be published in peer-reviewed academic journals;
 - be written in English;
 - be published between 2015 and 2025;
 - focus on digital transformation, healthcare digitalization, or organizational adaptation within healthcare contexts;
 - provide empirical findings or theoretical contributions relevant to healthcare management and organizational performance.
- Studies were excluded if they:
- were unrelated to healthcare settings;
 - focused exclusively on technical system design without organizational relevance;
 - lacked empirical or theoretical significance;
 - consisted of conference abstracts, editorials, or non-peer-reviewed materials.

Following the initial database search, duplicate records were removed, and the remaining studies were screened based on titles and abstracts. Full-text articles were subsequently assessed for eligibility according to the predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria. The final selection included studies that directly addressed digital transformation processes and organizational outcomes in primary healthcare settings.

The selected literature was analyzed using thematic synthesis methods. The analysis focused on identifying the major technological, organizational, and environmental factors influencing digital transformation, as well as examining their relationship with organizational performance and adaptation processes. Particular attention was given to studies addressing developing countries and emerging healthcare systems.

The study selection process conducted in accordance with PRISMA guidelines is summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. PRISMA-based study selection process¹

Stage	Description	Number
Identification	Records identified	420
Screening	Records screened	380
Eligibility	Full-text reviewed	110
Included	Final studies	52

This structured screening process ensured the inclusion of relevant and high-quality studies for analysis. The initial database search identified 420 articles. After removing duplicate records and screening titles and abstracts, 110 studies were selected for full-text review. Following the eligibility assessment based on the predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria, 52 articles were included in the final analysis.

¹ Author's development

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The analysis of the selected studies reveals that digital transformation in primary healthcare is shaped by three major categories of factors: technological, organizational, and environmental factors. The reviewed studies predominantly employ quantitative research methods, particularly survey-based designs, whereas qualitative and mixed-method approaches remain relatively limited. This indicates the need for more in-depth contextual and process-oriented investigations, especially in developing healthcare systems.

In addition, inadequate digital infrastructure and low-quality internet connectivity remain major barriers in many developing countries. Several studies emphasize that healthcare professionals are more likely to adopt and continuously use digital systems when technologies are user-friendly, efficient, and compatible with existing clinical processes [15]. Therefore, technological readiness is considered a foundational requirement for successful digital transformation.

Organizational factors such as leadership support, employee training, organizational culture, workload management, and workflow alignment also play a central role in digital transformation processes. The findings indicate that strong managerial commitment and continuous staff support contribute significantly to successful implementation and sustained technology use [18].

Conversely, misalignment between digital systems and clinical workflows often results in employee resistance, increased administrative workload, reduced productivity, and lower system acceptance. In several healthcare settings, insufficient user involvement during implementation processes created operational difficulties and reduced staff satisfaction [16]. These findings suggest that digital transformation should be managed not only as a technological initiative but also as an organizational change process requiring continuous adaptation and stakeholder engagement.

Environmental factors identified in the reviewed studies include government policy, regulatory frameworks, institutional support, financial resources, and broader healthcare system conditions. In developing countries, infrastructural limitations, inconsistent policy implementation, and limited funding significantly influence the success and sustainability of digital transformation initiatives [7].

The literature also highlights the importance of national digital health strategies, legal frameworks for data governance, and long-term investment policies in supporting healthcare digitalization. Countries with stronger institutional coordination and clearer regulatory systems tend to demonstrate more successful implementation outcomes [19].

The findings indicate that digital transformation has the potential to improve organizational efficiency, service quality, communication processes, and decision-making in primary healthcare institutions when systems are stable, user-friendly, and effectively integrated into clinical practice [12].

At the same time, several studies report that poorly implemented systems may increase administrative burden, create workflow disruptions, and reduce overall organizational performance. The effectiveness of digital transformation therefore depends not only on technological adoption but also on the quality of organizational adaptation, staff engagement, and environmental support mechanisms [21].

Overall, the reviewed evidence suggests that digital transformation in primary healthcare should be understood as a multidimensional and adaptive process requiring alignment between technology, organizational structures, and institutional conditions.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study conducted a systematic literature review to examine the key factors influencing digital transformation and its impact on organizational performance in primary healthcare settings. The findings indicate that digital transformation is a multidimensional and dynamic process shaped by the interaction of technological, organizational, and environmental factors.

From a theoretical perspective, the study highlights the limitations of traditional technology acceptance models and supports the application of dynamic theoretical approaches, such as Adaptive Structuration Theory, to better explain technology use and adaptation in complex and evolving healthcare environments. The findings demonstrate that digital transformation extends beyond the mere implementation of technology and involves continuous interaction between users, organizational structures, and institutional conditions.

From a practical perspective, the findings suggest that successful digital transformation requires not only technological investment but also organizational readiness, leadership support, staff training, reliable infrastructure, and continuous user support mechanisms. Healthcare organizations that effectively integrate digital systems into clinical workflows are more likely to achieve improvements in efficiency, service quality, and organizational performance.

Overall, this study contributes to the literature by providing a structured understanding of digital transformation processes in primary healthcare and offering a conceptual foundation for future empirical research. In addition, the study emphasizes the importance of context-specific implementation strategies to ensure the sustainable and effective integration of digital health systems in resource-constrained environments. These findings provide practical guidance for policymakers, healthcare managers, and institutional stakeholders seeking to enhance the effectiveness, adaptability, and long-term sustainability of digital transformation initiatives within primary healthcare systems.

REFERENCES

1. World Health Organization (2019). *Global Strategy on Digital Health 2020–2025*. Geneva: WHO.
2. World Bank (2023). *Digital-in-Health: Unlocking the Value for Everyone*. Washington, DC.
3. Government of Uzbekistan. (2020). *Digital Uzbekistan – 2030 Strategy*. Tashkent.
4. Vial, G. (2019). Understanding digital transformation: A review and research agenda. *Journal of Strategic Information Systems*, 28(2), 118–144.
5. Verhoef, P. C., Broekhuizen, T., Bart, Y., Bhattacharya, A., Dong, J. Q., Fabian, N., & Haenlein, M. (2021). Digital transformation: A multidisciplinary reflection and research agenda. *Journal of Business Research*, 122, 889–901.
6. Cresswell, K. M., & Aziz Sheikh (2013). Organizational issues in the implementation of health information technology in healthcare settings: A systematic review. *International Journal of Medical Informatics*, 82(5), e73–e86.
7. Sligo, J., Gauld, R., Roberts, V., & Villa, L. (2017). A literature review for large-scale health information system project planning, implementation and evaluation. *International Journal of Medical Informatics*, 97, 86–97.
8. Davis, F. D. (1989). Perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and user acceptance of information technology. *MIS Quarterly*, 13(3), 319–340.
9. Venkatesh, V., Morris, M. G., Davis, G. B., & Davis, F. D. (2003). User acceptance of information technology: Toward a unified view. *MIS Quarterly*, 27(3), 425–478.
10. DeSanctis, G., & Poole, M. S. (1994). Capturing the complexity in advanced technology use: Adaptive structuration theory. *Organization Science*, 5(2), 121–147.
11. Nilsen, P., Stahl, C., Roback, K., & Cairney, P. (2016). Never the twain shall meet? A comparison of implementation science and policy implementation research. *Implementation Science*, 11(1), 63.
12. Agarwal, R., Gao, G., DesRoches, C., & Jha, A. K. (2020). Research commentary—The digital transformation of healthcare: Current status and the road ahead. *Information Systems Research*, 31(3), 731–739.
13. Kruse, C. S., Stein, A., Thomas, H., & Kaur, H. (2018). The use of electronic health records to support population health: A systematic review. *JMIR Medical Informatics*, 6(2), e41.
14. Boonstra, A., Versluis, A., & Vos, J. F. J. (2014). Implementing electronic health records in hospitals: A systematic literature review. *BMC Health Services Research*, 14, 370.
15. Nguyen, L., Bellucci, E., & Nguyen, L. T. (2014). Electronic health records implementation: An evaluation of information system impact and contingency factors. *International Journal of Medical Informatics*, 83(11), 779–796.
16. Gagnon, M. P., Nsangou, É. R., Payne-Gagnon, J., Grenier, S., & Sicotte, C. (2014). Barriers and facilitators to implementing electronic health records: A systematic review. *Journal of Medical Systems*, 38(9), 1–13.
17. Trisha Greenhalgh, Wherton, J., Papoutsis, C., Lynch, J., Hughes, G., A'Court, C., Hinder, S., Fahy, N., Procter, R., & Shaw, S. (2017). Beyond adoption: A new framework for theorizing and evaluating nonadoption, abandonment, and challenges to the scale-up of health technologies. *Journal of Medical Internet Research*, 19(11), e367.
18. Sheikh, A., Anderson, M., Albala, S., Casadei, B., Franklin, B. D., Richards, M., Taylor, D., & Mossialos, E. (2021). Health information technology and digital innovation for national learning health and care systems. *The Lancet Digital Health*, 3(6), e383–e396.
19. Harrison, M. I., Koppel, R., & Bar-Lev, S. (2007). Unintended consequences of information technologies in health care—An interactive sociotechnical analysis. *Social Science & Medicine*, 65(8), 1606–1620.
20. Wanda Orlikowski (2000). Using technology and constituting structures: A practice lens for studying technology in organizations. *Organization Science*, 11(4), 404–428.

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Zokir ALIBEKOV

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Oloviddin Sobir o'g'li

2026. № 5 (3)

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelmasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

Mazkur jurnalda maqolalar chop etish uchun quyidagi havolalarga maqola, reklama, hikoya va boshqa ijodiy materiallar yuborishingiz mumkin. Materiallar va reklamalar pullik asosda chop etiladi.

EI.Pochta: sq143235@gmail.com

Bot: @iqtisodiyot_77

Tel.: 93 718 40 07

Jurnalga istalgan payt quyidagi rekvizitlar orqali obuna bo'lishingiz mumkin. Obuna bo'lgach, @iqtisodiyot_77 telegram sahifamizga to'lov haqidagi ma'lumotni skrinshot yoki foto shaklida jo'natishingizni so'raymiz. Shu asosda har oygi jurnal yangi sonini manzilingizga jo'natamiz.

"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

Jurnal sayti: <https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz>